

THE PROVISION OF ADEQUATE MATERIALS PROPERTY DATA

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ABSTRACT

The successful exploitation of new and improved engineering materials, including various forms of composite materials, depends on the availability of materials property data which are adequate in both quantity and quality. Although a significant amount of data for composite materials is available, there are a number of aspects of the subject which are currently less than satisfactory. The paper provides a broad overview of the current status of the subject, and addresses the following questions: What is needed? Why is it needed? How is it provided? What are the deficiencies? How should the situation be improved? Where do responsibilities lie? It deals with technical aspects in relatively broad terms, dealing with factors such as availability and standardisation of test methods, and the presentation and credibility of data. The paper concentrates on mechanical properties, and the discussion is given in the context of requirements for materials selection and product design. Important national and international initiatives are indicated.

1 INTRODUCTION

The current status of materials property data varies widely depending on the nature of the material and of the particular property. In some cases there is a mass of data provided by different materials suppliers, and the result for the potential user can be a situation which at worst is confusing and at best requires care and skill in its use. In other cases there is a dearth of relevant data, and in all cases there may be doubts about the validity, accuracy or relevance of the data. These deficiencies are more serious when the material is to be used in a demanding engineering application since there is then a greater need for accurate and relevant data.

Composite materials are relatively new engineering materials and they are recognised to have considerable potential for a wide range of engineering applications. Thus, there is a need for adequate materials property data, but the current status is that in general there is too little available data and full credibility of existing data has not yet been established. The situation is made more difficult by the fact that many applications require the material to be formed during product manufacture. Thus, there is no stock material from which accurate data can be obtained, and a combination of measurement and prediction may be required.

Materials property data are obtained by a wide variety of organisations including materials suppliers, test houses, research laboratories and end users. Furthermore, there are often a variety of test methods used to measure what is ostensibly the same property. This fragmentation and lack of harmonisation is responsible for a situation which, given the importance of composites and their applications, must be seen to be unsatisfactory.

In the present paper a number of fundamental questions are addressed: What is needed? Why is it needed? How is it provided? What are the deficiencies? How should the present situation be improved? Who should be involved? The motivation behind these questions is satisfaction of the technical requirements to facilitate the use of composites in industrial applications.

The paper gives a broad review of the subject, concentrating on broad principles rather than technical details. The latter are more appropriate to other specialised papers in this conference and elsewhere. Section 2 identifies the extent of the potential demand for data, the following section considers the nature of the need for data, and Section 4 then identifies the actual need for data. The various means by which data may be provided are discussed in Section 5. The current status of standard test methods for composites is addressed in Section 6, and the following section discusses the need for standardisation. The remaining sections deal respectively with the impact of computers, responsible organisations which should contribute to future developments, and the principal conclusions of the paper.

2 THE POTENTIAL NEED FOR DATA

Similar considerations apply to all materials employed in engineering applications, and much of the discussion here applies more widely than to composite materials. However, where illustration is required or where there are special issues, the paper concentrates on this latter broad class of materials. Composites may be considered in the following categories:

- * long/continuous fibre reinforced thermosets (eg GRP, CFRP)
- * long/continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics (eg carbon/PEEK)
- * short fibre reinforced thermoplastics (eg carbon/PEEK, glass/nylon)
- * short fibre reinforced thermosets (eg DMC, SMC)
- * metal matrix composites
- * fibre reinforced ceramics

The last two categories have a less well developed base of materials information including property data. Therefore, illustrations given in this paper concentrate on the better developed situation for polymer composites.

Application areas for these composite materials are very widely based, requiring various combinations of service performance and a wide range of property data. Thermosets with long/continuous fibre reinforcement have important applications in aerospace structures, marine vessels and structures, chemical plant pipes, vessels and tanks, and pipelines for oil, water and effluent distribution. These applications require appropriate combinations of light weight, corrosion resistance and structural integrity, coupled with manufacturing and maintenance advantages. They are used in a variety of multi-ply laminate forms utilising layers of uni-directional fibres, woven reinforcements, etc. Thermoplastics with long/continuous fibre reinforcement are likely to find applications in aerospace structures and land transport, provided that they can achieve the required performance and have production advantages. Short-fibre reinforced plastics have a wide range of existing and potential applications, often as substitutes for metals, and where the unreinforced polymer has inadequate performance in some respect. They have advantages of light weight, corrosion resistance and ease of manufacture, but some property

shortcomings may require special attention (for example, creep of thermoplastics).

Metal matrix composites are potentially light-weight materials (eg with aluminium matrices) compared with conventional alloys but with comparable properties. They may be preferred to reinforced polymers on the basis of their high temperature performance. Current principal applications under development are in aerospace structures and, despite the early interest in these materials, their property data and dependence on composite structure are not well documented. Technical ceramics are an even newer class of materials, with uses in high temperature applications such as engines and in corrosion and wear-resistant applications. They have some difficult properties, such as statistical strength and lower toughness, which may be improved by fibre reinforcement, but property definition and relevant data are at an early stage of development.

The wide range of potential applications for the various classes of composite materials implies a very high requirement for materials property data. This includes data relevant to manufacture as well as to in-service performance, materials information of a qualitative and quantitative nature, and data relevant to mechanical and non-mechanical properties. Although the other aspects are also important, this paper is concerned primarily with quantitative data for mechanical properties relevant to in-service performance of the material and product.

Within the narrower context of quantitative mechanical characterisation, there are a wide range of factors to be considered:

- * Special features of materials behaviour:
 - . viscoelasticity (time, rate and frequency dependence)
 - . nonlinearity (due to material response or large deflections)
 - . anisotropy (eg orthotropic or transversely isotropic)
 - . inhomogeneity (due to fibre/matrix composition or sandwich structures)
 - . variability (due to statistical nature of behaviour)
- * Modes of deformation/loading:
 - . tension, flexure, shear, compression, biaxial, etc.
- * Relevant materials properties:
 - . short term stiffness and strength
 - . creep deformation and creep rupture

- . dynamic stiffness and loss
- . fatigue, impact and toughness
- * Effect of environmental conditions:
 - . temperature dependence of properties
 - . loss of property due to ageing
 - . interaction between mechanical load and environment

If property data were required for all classes of composite materials, for all specific materials within each class, and for all of the factors listed above, then it is evident that a vast amount of data would be required. In fact, this apparently heavy requirement is a principal reason for the current status of the subject: fragmentation, lack of harmonisation, apparent chaos. There is a need for clarification of the real requirements, for rationalisation and standardisation of data production, and for appropriate action by relevant organisations.

3 THE USES FOR MATERIALS DATA

Any evaluation of the needs for materials property data must consider why the data are needed and how they are to be used in industrial applications. It is probably true that much materials data are obtained without a clear understanding of intended use. There is evidently an essential need for communication between the suppliers of data and end users in order that data are of the greatest value.

Materials property data are required for three principal purposes:

- * preliminary materials selection
- * processing and fabrication
- * product design

The discussion here concentrates on the first and third of these aspects, and it is important to note that their requirements are different. Data for preliminary materials selection needs to reflect only the essential features of the behaviour of the material, in order to indicate the suitability or otherwise of the material for the particular application and to provide an approximate ranking of competing materials. It should be recognised that mechanical properties are only one factor in materials selection (others being material cost, processibility, design expertise, need for capital investment, etc), so that an accurate ranking of materials from the point of view of mechanical properties may not be

Figure 1. Typical Young's modulus data for the main types of GRP material. The data envelopes shown refer to a wide range of different resin/glass systems and do not indicate the scatter of a particular GRP material (after [1]).

necessary for preliminary material selection. In contrast, data for product design needs to be more extensive, more detailed and more accurate. It is required to finalise materials selection, to determine values of design parameters and to predict product performance.

The discussion above suggests that there is a need for basic data for a wide range of materials to facilitate preliminary materials selection, and that this should be widely available. In general, it is adequate for this to be single-point data, for example a short-term modulus value to indicate stiffness and a further parameter to indicate the extent of creep behaviour. The latter could be the ratio of the modulus after say one

Figure 2. Typical tensile strength values for the main types of GRP material. The data envelopes shown refer to a wide range of different resin/glass systems and do not indicate the scatter of a particular GRP material (after [1]).

year to the short-term modulus (rather than a full creep curve), a value near to one indicating low creep, etc. Other properties, such as resistance to aggressive environments, could be given in purely qualitative form (pass/fail).

Data for detailed product design must be appropriate to the precise material used in the product and to the intended service environment and loading conditions. The problem is indicated in Figs 1 and 2 which show property envelopes for stiffness and strength of a number of GRP materials. The variability in properties for materials with a given volume fraction of reinforcing fibres is due to differences in precise fibre and matrix

specifications, to differences in specimen fabrication, and to differences in testing procedures. Thus, the diagrams are of value for indicating the range of properties available with these materials, and the probable difficulty in achieving the upper limits. However, they are of little use for detailed product design because of the wide variation in properties (for example, a factor of two at the same volume fraction between the highest and lowest values) and the difficulty of choosing a value appropriate to the intended materials and processes. These more precise data are best obtained from property envelopes obtained for specific fibres, resins and/or processing routes, or from tests carried out specially for the system to be used.

4 THE ACTUAL NEED FOR DATA

Section 2 indicated the potential extent of the need for data, and Section 3 discussed the reasons for which materials data are required. Further consideration can indicate some ways in which the magnitude of the perceived requirement for data can be reduced. Principal factors are:

- * product service requirements
- * product sophistication
- * materials selection
- * compatibility with design procedures

Product service requirements dictate the type of property data which may be required in the design process. In practice, only a few of the factors listed in Section 2 are likely to be significant in any particular application. Stiffness data will almost always be required since it controls the distribution of stresses within the component (unless the system is statically determinate) and the resulting strains and displacements. In general, one aspect of product loading is likely to be predominant and this will determine whether strength, creep, fatigue, impact or toughness properties are the most relevant. Similarly, viscoelasticity, non-linearity, anisotropy, inhomogeneity and exposure to aggressive environments will be relevant in limited circumstances and rarely in combination of more than two.

Although only a few of the factors (and the relevant property data) are required in a given application, they are all potentially relevant in some applications. An identified reduction in the amount of data required

for a particular material could only be made if it can be established that the material is rarely or never used in a certain set of circumstances. To an extent, this process of limitation occurs in an ad hoc manner since much data are obtained only when they are demanded by a particular product development. However, a broad survey of requirements, on a material class and product basis, would serve to show where priorities lie and where there are important gaps in available data.

Within the discussion given above, an important factor is the level of sophistication of the product. For example, the level of design analysis and necessary property data will be much greater for an aerospace component in CFRP than for a sailing dinghy in GRP. In less sophisticated or demanding applications certain aspects of behaviour will be ignored and therefore the associated property data will not be required. For example, it would be very unlikely that the design process for a product fabricated from short-fibre reinforced thermoplastics would take explicit account of nonlinearity, anisotropy or inhomogeneity.

The requirements of preliminary materials selection have been discussed in the previous Section and it has been noted that the requirement is for basic data (eg single-point data) giving broad characteristics rather than for detailed (eg multi-point) data. Property ranges are ideal information, for example presented in the format of Figs 1 and 2, although property ranges related to fewer variables (fibre type, resin type, processing route) would be more useful.

A particularly important influence on the requirement for property data is the need for compatibility with the design procedure which is to be used. This may involve use of a relevant design formula (for example, from [2]), use of a relevant product specification or code of practice (for example, [3]) or use of a computer-aided design (CAD) software package (for example, [4] [5]). In general all of these procedures use models of materials behaviour that are much simpler than available materials data. This implies a loss of detailed characterisation and accuracy, but it also highlights the fact that it is pointless to measure more detailed data if they cannot then be used in the design process. Design formulae, product specifications and codes of practice will rarely require more than

parameters such as Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and design factors such as the k-parameters in [3]. CAD techniques, although capable of handling greater geometrical complexity, currently contain materials models which are relatively crude (for example, for viscoelastic and nonlinear effects). Anisotropy can be handled adequately, for linear behaviour, but it will be rare that all twenty-one stiffness parameters will be required for any anisotropic material! This has an obvious consequence for property data requirements.

In conclusion it can be stated that the actual need for property data is significantly less than the potential need identified in Section 2. Only certain properties are important for particular classes of materials and applications. In general, data in handbooks or datasheets should be restricted to data required for materials selection, and for this only broad characteristics are required. Data for design should wherever possible be obtained specifically for the particular material, process and product, and should be confined to data actually required by the service conditions and design procedures. This requires the existence of suitable procedures for acquiring the relevant data.

5 THE PROVISION OF DATA

Necessary materials property data can be provided through three procedures:

- * direct measurement
- * deduction from other measurements
- * calculation

and they will be discussed here in reverse order.

In general, the calculation of materials properties from first principles is very difficult, and often inaccurate, due to the complexity of materials structure. However, the nature of composite materials is such that property calculation is relatively simple when based on the known properties of the constituents (fibres and matrix) and their geometrical arrangement. In their simpler forms, the calculation procedures may involve approximations such as the rule of mixtures, upper and lower bounds to properties or theories which take more detailed account of the geometrical arrangement of fibre distribution (see [6]). These procedures allow predictions to be made of composite properties for monolithic

materials and for the lamina from which laminates are constructed. Laminate theory is well-developed (see [7]) and laminate design calculations have been incorporated into a number of commercially available computer software packages (see [8] [9]). However, the level of variation of properties which can occur in real materials with supposedly similar constituents and structure (cf Figs 1, 2) indicates that calculated properties should be regarded as approximations requiring experimental verification.

The potentially heavy requirement for measured property data makes it particularly attractive if certain properties can be deduced from other measurements without the need for further testing. Obvious examples are extrapolation and interpolation of measured data, for example the interpolation of creep data at a new stress level from data at higher and lower stresses. Other less obvious examples are inter-conversion, acceleration and the use of superposition principles. An example of the first is the calculation of stress-relaxation properties of plastics from creep data. Accelerated tests, for example durability tests for assessing resistance to long term exposure to various environments, claim to deduce properties under one set of conditions (eg normal exposure over long times) from measurements under another set of conditions (exaggerated exposure over short times). Other tests use the inter-relation between, for example, the effects of time and temperature to deduce the properties of plastics at long times from measurements made at elevated temperatures. Many such procedures are used to provide and extend property data, and they are useful if their validity is known. One of the VAMAS projects (see Section 9) is concerned with this subject.

The most satisfactory method of data production is direct measurement, and it must be used when calculation and deduction cannot be used or need to be verified. Direct measurement of materials properties requires the existence of an appropriate set of test methods including procedures for data analysis. Calibration of the test equipment may require the provision of (certified) reference materials, and presented data should be accompanied by a statement of the conditions under which it was obtained. The current status of standard test methods for the mechanical properties of composites is discussed in the next Section.

6 STANDARD TEST METHODS

The technical literature abounds with papers on the development of particular test methods and the analysis of data for particular composite systems. Some of these papers provide limited comparisons between alternative test methods for the same property (for example [10]). It is beyond the scope of the present paper to review this technical literature. A more tractable objective is an assessment of the status of current standard test methods. These standards have a much greater value (see Section 7) and they are relatively few in number.

The details of a particular test method depend of course on the properties to be determined, but also on the nature of the material. Thus, it must be recognised that different standard tests must be provided for the major materials classes (metals, plastics, ceramics, etc). However, there may also be the need for different tests for different materials within the same broad class, for example for reinforced and unreinforced plastics. In this context, the requirement for separate tests may be due to the level of isotropy/anisotropy or to problems associated with materials structure. The differences are often manifested through the choice of test specimen size, shape, etc and may also influence the test itself.

For unreinforced rigid plastics there is a wide range of national and international standard tests for materials properties. The ISO tests for mechanical properties are shown in Table 1 and detailed references are given in [11]. The only significant omissions are fatigue and compressive creep, but these properties are covered in ASTM test methods [12]. Various national standards (BSI, DIN, ASTM, AFNOR, etc) are equivalent to the ISO procedures or provide alternative methods, and the lack of full harmonisation of these standard tests (for mechanical and non-mechanical properties) is discussed in Section 7.

Although these tests were developed for unreinforced materials, it should be recognised that almost all commercial plastics contain fillers and additives such as pigments, antioxidants and plasticisers. The fillers may take the form of particles or short fibres and there is only a vague distinction in some cases between a filled and a reinforced plastic. However, provided that the materials remain sensibly isotropic and do not

TABLE 1

ISO tests for mechanical properties of rigid plastics

Property	ISO test method
Tensile (short term)	R527
Flexural (short term)	178
Compressive (short term)	604
Tensile creep	899
Flexural creep	6602
Impact	179,180,6603
Damping/complex modulus	6721

contain structural features on a macroscopic scale which significantly affect their mechanical behaviour, they may continue to be regarded simply as rigid plastics and the tests listed in Table 1 may be used. (Note that cellular plastics, containing air or gas as "fillers", are no longer rigid materials and require a different set of tests.) Thus, for example, plastics such as nylon and polypropylene containing very short glass fibres (injection moulding grades) may be tested using the methods listed in Table 1, but with special requirements on the production of test specimens (for example [13]) to avoid misleading processing effects.

Plastics reinforced with long or continuous fibres involve features which invalidate the tests discussed above, and they therefore require a different set of standard test methods. Relevant factors are material anisotropy, the fact that loads in a single direction may produce twisting or lateral movement of the specimen, and edge effects due to fibres being cut at specimen edges. Relevant international and national standards are shown in Table 2 and detailed references are given in [14-17].

In view of the fact that there are more properties to be measured for composites, comparison of Tables 1 and 2 indicates that standard tests for plastics composites are much less developed than those for

TABLE 2

Standard tests for mechanical properties of plastics composites

Property	ISO	ASTM	BSI	DIN
Tensile (short term)	3268	D3039	2782/320E,F 2782/1003	EN61
Flexural (short term)	3597	D790	2782/1004	EN63
Compressive (short term)	3605	D3410	-	-
Shear (short term)	-	D2344 D3846	2782/341A	53463
Fatigue (tensile)	-	D3479	-	-

unreinforced plastics. In particular, there appear to be no current standard tests for creep and impact properties of composites, and the fatigue test is for tension rather than flexure. These are important properties for many applications of high performance composites, creep being particularly important for thermoplastic composites, and provision of relevant standard tests should be a high priority. Furthermore, the situation is not even as satisfactory as appears to be indicated in Table 2, since most of the referenced standard tests apply only to specific composite structures (for example, unidirectional, $0^\circ/90^\circ$, random or orthotropic reinforcements).

The tests for short-term properties referenced in Tables 1 and 2 use constant rates of loading which permit stiffness and strength values to be determined in a matter of seconds. In principle, similar test arrangements and specimen geometries could be used for short-term, creep and fatigue tests, provided that test and specimen parameters were suitably chosen. Proposals of this form have been made by the UK Ministry of Defence Composites Research Advisory Group (CRAG) (see [18]) and they may form the basis of future national and international standards. Two of the VAMAS projects (see Section 9) are seeking to develop standard tests for delamination and fatigue of plastics composites, and there are other research programmes under way.

Examination of ASTM standards identifies only one standard test method for metal matrix composites [19], namely for tensile properties, and no standard test methods are known for the mechanical properties of fibre reinforced ceramics. It can be anticipated that applications of these materials will stimulate the demand for standard data and tests, but it is evident that the subject is even less developed than for fibre reinforced plastics.

7 THE NEED FOR STANDARDISATION

Standard test methods are one aspect of a wider standards infrastructure which aids the exploitation of materials and the manufacture of products. A distinction should be made [20] between measurement standards of length, time, mass, etc (étalons in French) and documentary standards (normes in French). The latter are composed of:

- * standard glossaries and classifications
- * standard methods
- * standard specifications
- * standard codes of practice

Specifications include those for materials, processes and products, and methods include materials and product test methods. Thus, the standard test methods discussed in Section 6 are part of a hierarchy of standards.

The purposes of standards are to facilitate communication at many levels and to improve efficiency. Specifications and codes of practice are used as the basis for contracts between suppliers and customers, and they may be referred to in legislation and regulations or may be used on a "deemed to satisfy" basis. Standards are valuable in the technical context to facilitate the interaction between the various participants in the manufacturing process: materials suppliers, designers, manufacturers and end users.

In the context of the provision of materials property data, standardised test methods are important to ensure comparability of data from different sources and compatibility with other procedures (for example, materials selection and product design). Data from non-standardised test methods can be valuable within the limited context, and is usually the only form

of data available in the early stages of development of new materials. However, there are significant advantages for trade and technical development if standardised procedures can be introduced as soon as possible. In the present context there are two important forms of standardisation.

- * harmonisation of standard test methods
- * standardisation of data presentation

In the normal course of developments for new materials, non-standard test methods are followed by agreement on standard methods. Such standards may be produced at industry or national level initially and, consequently, several "standard" methods may be current at the same time (company, BSI, ASTM, DIN, ISO, etc). This situation can cause confusion due to lack of comparability of data from different sources, and it is evidently desirable to harmonise standard methods in order to achieve a unique standard. An example of a harmonisation exercise is work carried out by the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) on behalf of the British Plastics Federation (BPF) to identify an agreed set of tests for the properties of plastics, including filled materials. Recommendations for single-point data [21] and multi-point data [22] have been made and will form the basis of a new standard. It was evident from the discussion in Section 6 that a full set of standards for composites properties does not exist at present, and harmonisation of existing standards has not occurred yet.

Standardisation of data presentation is also important since it facilitates materials selection. In its simplest form, data are presented in data sheets and there are obvious advantages if the formats of the sheets provided by different materials suppliers are identical. This should include the order in which the different properties are presented, the form of presentation and any additional notes on test methods used, choice of test parameters, etc. Obviously this is simpler if a standard set of tests is used. The NPL/BPF project referred to above includes recommendations on data presentation.

The comments made above on harmonisation of tests and standardisation of data presentation were made in the context of individual materials classes (polymer composites, plastics, ceramics, etc). However, since material selection may involve more than one materials class, there would be extra benefits if standardisation could be achieved across materials classes.

This will be difficult due to the different characteristics of the behaviour of different types of materials, but it is a worthwhile long-term objective.

Finally, it is noted that the credibility of materials data can also benefit from standardised test methods. In addition to the test methods themselves, credibility of data depends on the competence of the organisations carrying out the testing and the quality of their equipment. These aspects can be assured by recognised calibration of instruments and accreditation of testing laboratories. In the UK this is achieved through the National Measurement Accreditation Service (NAMAS, not to be confused with VAMAS!) which is composed of the British Calibration Service (BCS) and the National Testing Laboratory Accreditation Scheme (NATLAS). Accreditation is facilitated when standard test methods are used.

8 THE USE OF COMPUTERS

Computers are used in a number of aspects of the subject discussed in this paper:

- * control of tests and analysis of data
- * databanks including facilities for materials selection
- * programs for laminate analysis
- * computer-aided design
- * expert systems

As the use of computers for control of tests and for analysis of data becomes more common, with relevant hardware and software being supplied with test equipment, it is appropriate that this should become a part of the standardised test methods. The use of computers in product and material design has been mentioned already in Sections 4 and 5.

An important use of computers is that of databanks including facilities for materials selection (for example [23-25]). With the increasing choice of materials available to the designer, computer-based materials selection is becoming the only tractable procedure. However, it should be recognised that it has attendant dangers. Early computer databanks have been formed by amassing data from many different sources, and often too little attention has been given to credibility and comparability of the data.

Unless these latter factors are assured, the basis for materials selection is of doubtful validity, although this fact may not be obvious to the user.

It is even more important when data are stored in a computer databank that the data should have been obtained using standard test methods, that these test methods should have been harmonised, that the definitions of properties should be identified, that a standard form of presentation should be used, that the credibility of the supplier of data should have been established, and that any qualifications applying to the data should be clearly indicated. It is probably true that no existing databank satisfies all of these requirements, and therefore that appropriate developments are necessary. This will involve technical aspects, standardisation, accreditation and development of appropriate computer procedures and standards, and it will involve the participation of various types of organisation (see Section 9). Only in this way will computer databanks become fully effective, enabling the designer to use them with confidence.

An important extension of databanks and CAD procedures is the development of computer-based expert systems. They provide an interactive facility, containing both qualitative and quantitative information, which can guide the user through materials selection and into product and process design. Expert systems are being developed for specific application areas (for example, design of metallic components in corrosive environments [26]), and it is evident that they must contain or have access to adequate materials data. In fact, expert systems, including databanks and CAD packages, will be developed in modular form and it is essential that they should have standardised interfaces in order to permit interaction between systems.

9 RESPONSIBLE ORGANISATIONS

Many organisations influence the production of adequate materials property data, and they can be discussed under the following headings:

- * industry
- * standards organisations
- * trade federations
- * governments

- * research bodies
- * international programmes (eg VAMAS)

Materials supply industries make the largest contribution to the provision of materials property data, through datasheets and databanks, and user industries should play an important part in defining the needs for data. Both industrial sectors are supported in these activities by test houses and research laboratories. Standards organisations (eg ISO, BSI, ASTM, DIN) have the primary responsibility for the production of relevant standard test methods, although policy and priority involves wider participation. Trade federations should act on behalf of industry sectors and can take a wider view than individual companies (for example the BPF harmonisation project referred to in Section 7). It can be argued that governments should be involved in policy formulation and in ensuring the existence of the necessary technical infrastructure required by broad sectors of manufacturing industry. They also have an indirect influence through the requirements imposed by legislation and by various certification and accreditation schemes (eg NAMAS).

Because of the technical nature of the subject discussed in this paper, it is evident that research bodies have a significant part to play, for example, through the provision of data, the development of test methods, and in scientific evaluation. The latter aspect includes the proper definition of properties, verification of the validity and accuracy of procedures, and support for calibration and accreditation procedures. These research contributions are more likely to be effective if they are a planned part of a national or international programme.

A relevant international project is the Versailles project on advanced materials and standards (VAMAS), which involves collaboration between the UK, USA, Canada, CEC, Japan, Italy, FRG and France on research directed at the provision of improved standards. Currently eleven technical working areas in the broad materials field have been approved, and those of particular relevance here are indicated in Table 3. The project on polymer composites is evaluating tests for delamination (an extension of an ASTM project) and for fatigue. The project on polymer properties is considering procedures for accelerating tests or extrapolating data (cf Section 5), the former in the context of durability assessment and

TABLE 3
VAMAS Projects relevant to this paper

VAMAS Project	VAMAS Lead	UK Lead
Polymer Composites Polymer Properties Materials Databanks	Bathias, France Lockett, UK Rumble, USA Kroekel, CEC	Sced, NPL Partridge, Cranfield Reynard, Wilkinson Consultants

the latter with respect to creep, stress-relaxation and fatigue behaviour. A broad review is being made in the materials databank project of the needs for standardisation with respect to both materials and computer aspects.

10 CONCLUSIONS

- (a) The current status of the subject is uneven; with insufficient data for some materials and properties, and with a mass of data in other areas leading to possible confusion or to the need for care and skill in its use.
- (b) Fragmentation of the sources and methods for data production pose important problems associated with credibility and comparability.
- (c) The situation for composite materials is complicated by the fact that materials and products are often formed in the same process, and supplier's data therefore has a reduced relevance.
- (d) The potential need for data is very great, depending on specific materials, processes, properties and service conditions.
- (e) Principal uses for data are materials selection and product design, and they impose different requirements. The former requires relatively basic data (eg single-point data), whereas the latter requires more detailed data which may need to be acquired for the specific application.

- (f) The nature of the application, its level of sophistication, and the type of product design procedures used, all dictate the type of data required. A global assessment of materials, applications and design procedures could lead to a planned reduction in the demand for data.
- (g) Property data may be provided by calculation, deduction and measurement, and each method has an important role.
- (h) The current set of test methods for composites is incomplete, and standardisation and harmonisation are important requirements.
- (i) Credibility, comparability and clarity of presentation of data are inadequate, needing to be improved and subjected to some form of accreditation.
- (j) The use of computers will provide significant benefits, but problems identified above become even more important and some new problems arise.
- (k) Many organisations are involved in various aspects of the subject, their contributions being largely ad hoc in nature, and great benefits would flow from a planned and coordinated approach.

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 - ISO 179 Plastics - Determination of Charpy impact strength
 - ISO 180 Plastics - Determination of Izod impact strength
 - ISO/R 527 Plastics - Determination of tensile properties
 - ISO 604 Plastics - Determination of compressive properties
 - ISO 899 Plastics - Determination of tensile creep
 - ISO 6602 Plastics - Determination of flexural creep by three-point bending
 - ISO 6603 Plastics - Determination of multi-axial impact behaviour
 - ISO 6721 Plastics - Determination of damping properties and complex modulus
- 12 ASTM test methods:
- D 671 Flexural fatigue of plastics by constant-amplitude-of-force.
 - D 2990 Tensile, compressive and flexural creep and creep rupture of plastics.
- 13 ISO 293 Plastics - Compression moulding test specimens of thermo-plastic materials.
- ISO 294 Plastics - Injection moulding test specimens of thermoplastic materials.
 - ISO 295 Plastics - Compression moulding test specimens of thermo-setting materials.
- 14 ISO test methods:
- ISO 3268 Plastics - Glass reinforced materials - Determination of tensile properties.
 - ISO 3597 Textile glass reinforced plastics - composites in the form of rods made from textile glass rovings - determination of flexural (cross breaking) strength.
 - ISO 3605 Textile glass reinforced plastics - composites in the form of rods made from textile glass rovings - determination of compressive strength.
- 15 ASTM test methods:
- D 790 Flexural properties of unreinforced and reinforced plastics and electrical insulating materials.
 - D 2344 Apparent interlaminar shear strength of parallel fiber composites by short beam method.
 - D 3039 Tensile properties of fiber resin composites.
 - D 3410 Compressive properties of unidirectional and crossply fiber-resin composites.

- D 3479 Tension-tension fatigue of oriented fiber resin matrix composites.
- D 3846 In-plane shear strength of reinforced plastics.
- 16 BSI test methods:
- BS 2782 Methods of testing plastics.
- 320E Tensile strength, fibre reinforced materials.
 - 320F Tensile strength of unidirectional reinforced materials.
 - 341A Determination of apparent interlaminar shear strength of reinforced plastics.
 - 1003 Glass reinforced plastics: determination of tensile properties.
 - 1004 Glass reinforced plastics: determination of flexural properties by three point bend method.
- 17 DIN test methods:
- DIN EN 61 Textile glass reinforced plastics: Determination of tensile properties.
- DIN EN 63 Glass reinforced plastics: Determination of flexural properties, three point method.
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- 26 Achilles Club: Expert systems on corrosion and corrosion control, National Corrosion Service, National Physical Laboratory, Teddington, Middlesex.